

- Amanda, M., & Lustosa, T. (2024). *UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DO MARANHÃO Programa de Pós-Graduação em Ciência da Computação FRAMEWORK GAMIA EDU: UM SISTEMA EDUCACIONAL GAMIFICADO, PERSONALIZADO E ADAPTADO AO ALUNO* São Luís.
- Bucchiarone, A. (2022). Gamification and virtual reality for digital twin learning and training: architecture and challenges. *Virtual Reality & Intelligent Hardware*, 4(6), 471–486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vrih.2022.08.001>
- Dahalan, F., Alias, N., & Shaharom, M. S. N. (2024). Gamification and Game Based Learning for Vocational Education and Training: A Systematic Literature Review. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29(2), 1279–1317. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11548-w>
- Gomaa, Y., Moussa, S., Lahoud, C., & Abel, M.-H. (2024). Exploring Recommender Systems for Assisting Teachers in E-Learning Gamification. *Procedia Computer Science*, 246, 2312–2321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.09.556>
- Han, X. (2025). Research on english E-learning teaching model based on digital entertainment and gamification experience: Interactive teaching experience. *Entertainment Computing*, 52, 100867. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.entcom.2024.100867>
- Hmoud, A. Y. R., Salah, O. H., & Altalib, R. A. H. (2024). The adoption of gamification in higher education and its impact on academic performance: empirical evidence from Jordan and Palestine. *Cogent Education*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2428907>
- Ivanjko, T., Pavlina, K., & Grubješić, I. (2020). *THE ROLE OF GAMIFICATION IN LANGUAGE LEARNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION*. 4926–4932. <https://doi.org/10.21125/inted.2020.1349>
- Liu, R., Benitez, J., Zhang, L., Shao, Z., & Mi, J. (2024). Exploring the influence of gamification-enabled customer experience on continuance intention towards digital platforms for e-government: An empirical investigation. *Information & Management*, 61(5), 103986. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2024.103986>
- Metwally, A. H. S., Nacke, L. E., Chang, M., Wang, Y., & Yousef, A. M. F. (2021). Revealing the hotspots of educational gamification: An umbrella review. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 109, 101832. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2021.101832>
- Ruiz, J. J. R., Sanchez, A. D. V., & Figueredo, O. R. B. (2024). Impact of gamification on school engagement: a systematic review. *Frontiers in Education*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2024.1466926>
- Song, S. (2022). *Gamification and User Engagement on Digital Platforms*.
- Unternährer, C., Termine, F., & De Santo, A. (2024). Enhancing Knowledge Transmission: The Perspective of Gamification User Profiles. *Procedia Computer Science*, 239, 1115–1123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.06.277>
- Vrcelj, A., Hoić-Božić, N., & Dlab, M. H. (2023). Use of Gamification in Primary and Secondary Education: A Systematic Literature Review. *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, 9(1), 13–27. <https://doi.org/10.12973/ijem.9.1.13>
- Wirani, Y., Nabarian, T., & Romadhon, M. S. (2022). Evaluation of continued use on Kahoot! as a gamification-based learning platform from the perspective of Indonesia students. *Procedia Computer Science*, 197, 545–556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.12.172>
- Xiao, Y., & Hew, K. F. (2024). Personalised gamification enhances student participation but produces mixed effects on emotional and cognitive engagements: a systematic review. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 32(10), 7014–7040. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2023.2299977>
- Zhu Jin, Zhou Yue, Gao Chao, & Peng Yuanqiu. (2024). The Influence of Gamification Teaching Strategies to Skills Acquisition of Students among Selected Vocational School in China. *Journal of Computer Science and Technology Studies*, 6(3), 115–135. <https://doi.org/10.32996/jcsts.2024.6.3.11>

